

Electrochemical Reduction of Tellurite Ion at DME in Aqueous-Organic Solvent Mixtures

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The present investigation deals with the polarographic reduction of tellurite ion (TeO_3^{2-}) in aqueous, aqueous-methanol, aqueous-ethanol and aqueous-dioxan mixtures. The reduction has been found to be diffusion controlled as verified by i_d vs $\sqrt{h}$ and i_d vs C (concentration of TeO_3^{2-} ion) plots, which were linear and passing through origin in all cases. The plots of $\log(i/i_d - i)$ vs $E_{d.c.}$ (vs. S.C.E.) were linear in all the systems, but the values of slopes were much higher than required for six electron reduction (10 mV). These observations indicate the irreversible nature of electrode reduction. The kinetics of electrode process has been studied using Gellings' method and modified Koutecky's treatment. The values of kinetic parameters have been determined (K_s , K_m° , and α). These values further confirm irreversible nature of reduction of TeO_3^{2-} ion. The nature of reduction has considerably been effected by changing the solvent composition. There is no significant change in α values with addition of organic solvent, so it is probably that there is no change in the mechanism of the electrode process. The analytical importance of the results obtained have been discussed.

POLAROGRAPHY has been widely used for the reduction of cations in different solvents¹⁻⁶.

However, the studies with the reduction of anions are only a few. The reduction of chromate, tellurate and iodate have been studied by Sadek *et al*⁷ in aqueous alkanol mixtures and aqueous-dioxan mixtures. The reduction of chromate, bromate and iodate has been studied in detail in our laboratory by Gaur *et al*⁸⁻⁹. Lingane *et al*¹⁰ studied the reduction of Te(IV) using ammoniacal buffer solutions. The reduction of Te(IV) in alkaline medium has been studied by Jamieson *et al*¹¹. These authors indicated six electron reduction process and have discussed mechanism of the process.

Present paper deals with the polarographic reduction of TeO_3^{2-} in aqueous, aqueous-methanol, aqueous-ethanol and aqueous-dioxan media. The nature of electrode process being irreversible, the kinetic parameters have been calculated using Gellings'¹² theoretical treatment and modified Koutecky's¹³ method.

Experimental

Stock solutions of tellurite ions (M/40), sodium hydroxide (1.0 M) and 0.2% gelatin were prepared by dissolving the required weight of reagent grade Na_2TeO_3 , NaOH and gelatin in doubly distilled water. Solutions containing 0.5 mM tellurite ions, 0.1 M sodium hydroxide, 0.008% gelatin and required volume of organic solvent were taken. The

current voltage curves were obtained by a manual set up. The DME having m 3.025 mg/sec and $t=2.7$ sec (at 55 cm of mercury pressure) in 0.1 M NaOH with applied potential of 1.0 V (vs. S.C.E.) was used during all the measurements. The experiments were performed at 25 ± 0.1 which was maintained with a Haake type ultrathermostat. The solutions were freed from dissolved oxygen by bubbling purified N_2 gas for 20 minutes. Methanol, ethanol and dioxan were purified using methods suggested by Bard¹⁴.

Results and Discussion

The reduction was found to be diffusion controlled in each system which was confirmed by plotting the graph between i_d vs h and i_d vs C (conc. of tellurite ions). These plots were linear and pass through origin. The plots of $\log(i/i_d - i)$ vs $E_{d.c.}$ (S.C.E.) were linear in all cases and the slope values were higher than required for six electron reversible reduction (10 mV). This indicated the irreversible nature of electrode process. Hence reversible half wave potentials ($E_{1/2}^r$) has been calculated by using Gellings' treatment (Table 1). The values of kinetic parameters (standard rate constant K_s and transfer coefficient α) have also been evaluated by Gellings' method. Forward rate constant K_m° and transfer coefficient have also been calculated by Koutecky's method as extended by Gaur and Bhargava¹³ (summarised in Table 2). The trend of variation of the values of transfer coefficient (α) by both the methods are nearly the same.

TABLE 1—SOLVENT EFFECT ON POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF TELLURITE WAVE IN 0.1 M NaOH

Sl. No.	Solvent	Percentage (by volume)	id(μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V vs S.C.E.)	Slope (mV)	$D^{1/2} \times 10^3$ cm ² /sec	$-E_{1/2}^r$ (in volts)
1.	Methanol	10.0	12.15	1.2270	58	1.3886	1.2070
		20.0	10.80	1.2240	62	1.2028	1.1910
		30.0	10.08	1.2145	82	1.1226	1.1640
		40.0	9.63	1.2105	128	1.0780	1.1450
		50.0	9.45	1.2046	138	1.0624	1.1290
2.	Ethanol	10.0	11.88	1.2185	53	1.3265	1.1920
		20.0	9.99	1.2245	60	1.1154	1.1980
		30.0	9.36	1.2450	62	1.0487	1.2100
		40.0	8.91	1.2595	65.5	0.9982	1.2230
		50.0	8.19	1.2720	66	0.9184	1.2330
3.	Dioxan	10.0	10.98	1.2400	48	1.3218	1.2185
		20.0	10.71	1.2680	55	1.1999	1.2315
		30.0	10.26	1.2740	44	1.1505	1.2435
		40.0	8.82	1.2910	48	0.9890	1.2585
		50.0	8.19	1.3100	52	0.9199	1.2850
4.	Water	—	12.51	1.2200	35	1.3921	1.2000

TABLE 2—SOLVENT EFFECT ON KINETIC PARAMETERS OF TELLURITE ION IN 0.1 M NaOH

Sl. No.	Solvent	Percentage (by volume)	Gellings Treatment		Modified Koutecky's Method	
			αn	K ^o s $\times 10^4$ cm sec ⁻¹	αn	K ^o _{th} cm sec ⁻¹
1.	Methanol	10.0	1.35	3.554	0.98	4.230×10^{-24}
		20.0	1.20	2.084	0.91	8.478×10^{-23}
		30.0	0.9	1.972	0.69	4.375×10^{-18}
		40.0	0.6	1.078	0.44	5.986×10^{-13}
		50.0	0.6	1.062	0.41	2.999×10^{-12}
2.	Ethanol	10.0	1.20	2.911	1.07	7.066×10^{-26}
		20.0	1.20	2.152	0.91	2.529×10^{-25}
		30.0	0.90	2.240	0.91	3.543×10^{-23}
		40.0	0.90	2.211	0.86	2.222×10^{-23}
		50.0	0.90	2.043	0.86	1.862×10^{-23}
3.	Dioxan	10.0	1.20	3.964	1.18	1.132×10^{-28}
		20.0	0.90	2.568	1.03	5.587×10^{-26}
		30.0	1.35	2.276	1.29	1.135×10^{-31}
		40.0	1.20	1.961	1.18	9.322×10^{-30}
		50.0	1.05	1.454	1.09	3.789×10^{-28}
4.	Water	—	1.65	2.855	1.62	2.812×10^{-27}

It is a general observation that diffusion current decreases as the percentage of solvent increases from 10% to 50% (by volume). This change in diffusion current is due to viscosity effect by applying Ilkovic-Stoke relation, $idn^{1/2} = \text{constant}$. The apparent decrease at higher proportions of the organic solvent can be ascribed to solvation of ions by the bulky organic molecules and the decreased solubility of the reducible salts.

The values of $E_{1/2}$ and $E_{1/2}^r$ have been found to shift in more cathodic direction as the percentage of ethanol and dioxan increases. However, the reverse trend is observed in case of methanol solvent. The shift in $E_{1/2}$ value with solvent has been discussed by Sadek *et al*⁷ but no unified theory has been given so far. For reversible systems the difference in half

wave potentials ($\Delta E_{1/2}$) due to transfer of the depolarizer from solvent 1 to solvent 2, as derived by Takahashi⁵ using Born equation given as :

$$\Delta E_{1/2} = (E_{1/2})_2 - (E_{1/2})_1 = \frac{Ze}{Zr} \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon_2} - \frac{1}{\epsilon_1} \right) \quad \dots (1)$$

But for irreversible system introducing standard electrode potential

$$(E_{1/2})_2 - (E_{1/2})_1 = \frac{Ze}{2} \left(\frac{\epsilon_2 - 1}{\epsilon_2 r_2} - \frac{\epsilon_1 - 1}{\epsilon_1 r_1} \right) + \frac{0.059}{na}$$

$$\log \frac{(1.349Kst^{1/2})_2}{Do^{1/2}_2} - \log \frac{(1.349Kst^{1/2})_1}{Do^{1/2}_1} \quad \dots (2)$$

Equation (2) indicates that the shift in the $E_{1/2}$ of an irreversible electrode reaction during the transfer

from one solvent to another is governed not only by the dielectric constant, but also by the change in the effective radius of the ion, and the kinetic parameters of the reaction. Accordingly, it is not easy to predict the magnitude of the $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ shift of an irreversible process caused by changing the solvent. Irregular behaviour may also be due to the change of liquid, liquid junction potential, chemical nature of the solvent and ion-pair formation.

It has been observed that there is no significant change in the value of α_n with addition of organic solvent; so it is probable that there is no change in the mechanism of the electrode reaction suggested by Lingane *et al.*¹⁰ i.e., six electron reduction in very alkaline solutions

The structure of double layer also plays an important role in the reduction of anions. The specific adsorption of anions at more cathodic potentials, the existence of the bulky organic molecule in the double layer, and the partial destruction of the aquo-layer surrounding the reducible ion, or its replacement by organic molecules make the reduction more difficult¹⁵. Hence the addition of organic solvent increases the irreversibility of the reduction which is obvious from Table 2.

The results are of analytical importance since tellurite ions can be estimated polarographically in the presence of organic solvents (methanol, ethanol and dioxan). Similarly tellurite ions can also be estimated in presence of other anions like arsenate, arsenite, molybdate, vanadate, selenate, etc. Tellurite can be estimated in trace quantity in 0.1 M NaOH in presence of these ions.

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